

The Impact of Social Support on the College Enrollment Aspirations of Ethnic Minority Vocational Students: A Case Study of a Modern Industrial College in Xinjiang

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ABSTRACT

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In recent years, China has been striving to enhance the quality of the population in ethnic minority areas, promote local talent cultivation, and accelerate local economic development by increasing investment in basic education resources and expanding enrollment in higher education. This study conducted semi-structured interviews with 27 ethnic minority students from a modern industrial college in Xinjiang to explore the influence of social support on academic aspirations. Employing qualitative research methods and drawing on the interview outline by Wang (2020), supported by Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior, the study concludes that national policies, schools, teachers, and parents influence the academic aspirations of ethnic minority students. Based on these findings, the study suggests the effective implementation of relevant national policies and calls for schools, teachers, and parents to pay attention to and encourage the academic aspirations of ethnic minority students. This study inspires future scholars to pay more attention to the academic aspirations of ethnic minority students, aiming to provide them with more assistance and improve the overall education level of ethnic minority students.

KEYWORDS:

Ethnic Minority Areas; Ethnic Minority; Vocational College Students; Social Support; Academic Aspirations

INTRODUCTION

China has 56 ethnic groups, among which the Han ethnic group is the largest, accounting for the vast majority of the population, while the other 55 minority ethnic groups are distributed across various regions. Some well-known ethnic

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minority regions include Tibet, Xinjiang, Inner Mongolia, Guangxi, and Yunnan, among others. These regions often exhibit diverse ethnic cultures in terms of language, religion, and other aspects, different from those of the Han ethnic areas, showcasing the diverse ethnic cultures of China. Guo et al. (2020) pointed out that in recent years, with strong support from the state and government, the per capita regional GDP of ethnic provinces and regions (including Inner Mongolia, Ningxia, Xinjiang, Qinghai, Tibet, Yunnan, Guizhou, and Guangxi, hereinafter referred to as "ethnic regions") has continued to grow rapidly, with an average annual growth rate of 12.75% from 2000 to 2020, far exceeding the national average growth rate. In addition, Sun

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(2023) analyzed in his study that from a macro perspective, the cultivation of the common consciousness of the Chinese nation in ethnic regions not only relates to the overall development and stability of the country and the internal driving force of creativity but also relates to the authority and fairness of national policies and legal norms. The common consciousness of ethnic groups demonstrates the importance of China progressing together as a whole. Economic development and improvement in living standards are inseparable from the development of education. Exploring the issue of ethnic minority students' further education highlights a certain significance of the times. Starting from the perspective of people in ethnic regions, broadening their national vision, improving their economic level, and enhancing the overall education level are crucial. From the current education system in China, graduates from vocational colleges can choose employment or continue their education through examinations to pursue undergraduate studies.

Ben (2023) points out that talent is a significant driver of technological innovation and a crucial factor in enhancing regional competitiveness. The substantial imbalance in development between regions is largely determined by disparities in educational and technological investment among regions. For instance, in ethnic minority areas, the proportion of people with high school education or above in Guizhou, Tibet, and Qinghai is lower than the national average, which is related to the inadequate local educational resources and insufficient emphasis on education. From the perspective of education, further education is one of the ways to develop and improve the overall education level of ethnic minority students in ethnic minority areas, and it is also one of the methods to base current and future economic development and promote social progress. In the strategic process of valuing youth work and developing education, Xi (2022) emphasized at the 20th National Congress of the Communist Party of China that the entire party should regard youth work as strategic work, arm young people with the party's scientific theories, inspire young people with the party's original mission, and be intimate friends of young people, enthusiastic participants in youth work, and guides for young people. Xiong and Ren (2022) elaborated on the vast territory, diverse social and cultural aspects, and the uneven development trend in terms of economic development level, urbanization development, scientific and

technological innovation capability, and degree of openness in ethnic minority areas. Against the backdrop of China's rapid development, this study focuses on ethnic minority vocational students in ethnic minority areas to explore the impact of social support on further education. By starting from the actual life and study situations, it fully understands the intention of ethnic students to continue their education after vocational college graduation, which not only raises the awareness of further education among ethnic students but also inspires some thoughts for policy makers, schools, educators, and parents as social support factors. These perspectives shed light on the importance of education from the perspectives of society, schools, and educators. This study conducts in-depth exploration and analysis on this theme.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social support

Social support plays a crucial role in various fields, including socioeconomic development, medicine, and mental health. However, there is relatively limited literature on social support related to academic aspirations. According to McLeod et al. (2020), social support refers to the assistance, support, and recognition individuals receive in social interactions, including tangible aid, emotional support, information provision, and the expansion and strengthening of social networks. Similarly, Zhao et al. (2022) point out that social support is typically divided into emotional support and instrumental support, with emotional support involving encouragement and motivation received by individuals. Many scholars have found that social support plays a significant role in life. Kim and Jeon (2019) summarize that social support can help individuals build self-esteem and self-confidence, increase happiness, and cope with stress and adversity, thereby promoting personal growth and development. Additionally, Zhang et al. (2021) indicate that research on the buffering mechanism of social support suggests that it provides important psychological resources for individuals, effectively replenishing depleted psychological energy, alleviating the impact of negative life events, and enhancing resilience and confidence in coping with difficulties. Furthermore, Akbasm et al. (2021) conclude that social support refers to individuals' perception of obtaining or potentially obtaining external support, and it is also a protective factor for physical and mental health.

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Studies have shown that low levels of social support are detrimental to physical and mental health, and patients with low levels of social support have higher fatigue scores.

According to Galindo and Losada (2023), social support can be divided into three subtypes: perceived family support, perceived peer support, and perceived teacher support. Özgül's study in 2023 indicated that higher levels of social support help individuals enhance their internal self-awareness and behavioral cognition, enabling them to more actively cope with difficulties and stress, thereby enhancing psychological resilience. Additionally, Pu et al. (2024) pointed out that social support is an externally sourced, visible, and objective emotional support from the environment, emphasizing individuals' subjective ability to perceive support and understanding from the external world. Regression analysis by He (2024) showed that social support positively predicts subjective well-being, consistent with previous research findings. Liu and Zeng (2024) agreed with the findings of He (2024) regarding the impact of social support on youth. Liu and Zeng (2024) found that formal and informal perceived social support have stronger inhibitory effects on unemployment anxiety among young workers facing greater uncertainty. Additionally, Sun and Du (2024) concluded that perceived social support and self-efficacy are positively correlated with subjective well-being, and perceived social support is positively correlated with self-efficacy. Consistent with these findings, this study suggests that the educational aspirations of minority students may be influenced by social support from family, school, and other sources.

Therefore, these studies emphasize the importance of social support for individual mental health and well-being. In this context, schools and other relevant departments should prioritize the social support systems for college students, creating a favorable campus or social environment, providing support and understanding, and helping them better cope with life's challenges.

Intention to pursue further education

Research on the intention to pursue further education primarily originates from various schools. Gui et al. (2023) categorized the intention to pursue further education into four dimensions: behavioral attitude dimension, subjective norm dimension, perceived behavioral control dimension, and intention to enroll dimension. He and Xiao (2024)

pointed out that in the new era, it is essential to adhere to the talent cultivation model guided by the principle of "emphasizing both employment and further education," in order to enhance students' abilities for both employment and further education. Meanwhile, Kang and Gong (2024) argued that the intention to pursue further education is a complex issue, involving both individual internal factors and the influence of external factors on individuals. Therefore, when studying the factors affecting the intention to pursue further education, it is essential to consider both internal and external factors. This study believes that the advancement of minority vocational students in ethnic regions is advantageous for students, families, and the development of ethnic regions.

From the relevant studies on the intention to pursue further education, different scholars have made different findings. Zhu and Wu (2021) discovered that in terms of family environment, students from economically disadvantaged families have a higher proportion of subjective academic abandonment compared to students from affluent families. Also moreover, Gong et al. (2022) conducted statistical analysis on the intention of non-ethnic minority students to pursue undergraduate studies and found that among the effective samples, 85% of students (281 individuals) believed that pursuing undergraduate studies was necessary, while only 15% of students believed it was unnecessary. 72% of students were prepared to pursue undergraduate studies, while only 28% of students were not prepared. The research results reflect that the reasons for pursuing undergraduate studies are related to the number of job positions, thresholds, and promotion opportunities available to vocational college graduates.

The intention to pursue further education is closely related to social support. Wang and Chen (2023) found that the family's economic situation and educational level both have a highly significant positive regression effect on students' intention to pursue further education at the 0.001 level. At the school level, the level of resources and policies related to tuition waivers have a significant positive regression effect on students' intention to pursue further education at the 0.05 level. On the other hand, Tang (2023) constructed a model to analyze the influencing mechanisms of vocational school students' intention to pursue further education. The study found that vocational school students' intention to pursue further education is influenced by six

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factors: expected educational benefits, individual differences, significant others, internal environment, external environment, and national macro policies. Factors such as family capital, parental attitudes, and national macro policies have an impact on the intention to pursue further education. In this study, the intention to pursue further education is defined as the idea of minority students in vocational colleges in ethnic minority areas continuing their education to obtain a bachelor's degree. Le (2024) agreed with Tang (2023) regarding the influence of student advancement on parents. Le (2024), while studying student advancement issues, found that parental educational expectations play a moderating role in the relationship between children's academic pressure and parents' examination anxiety. This study defines the desire for further education as the idea of minority vocational students in ethnic regions continuing their studies to pursue a bachelor's degree. It explores the relationship between social support and the desire for further education, focusing on the specific student group of minority students, and analyzes from the perspective of social support how to increase the success rate of further education.

Some scholars have also proposed their views on this research topic, suggesting that measures can be taken to cultivate overall education levels and regional innovation capabilities. Li and Zhao (2023) recommend increasing education expenditure and improving the technology innovation system. They advocate for vigorously cultivating high-quality talents in ethnic regions to enhance regional research and development capabilities and promote the transformation and upgrading of traditional industries towards informatization, digitalization, and intelligentization. Meanwhile, Li (2023) discusses the importance of ideological and political education in ethnic regions, pointing out that many ethnic regions are located in remote areas, where teachers' professional awareness and abilities are relatively weak, and there are issues with inadequate teaching levels and standardized teaching management. These perspectives highlight the importance of education from the standpoint of society, schools, and education practitioners. This study conducts in-depth exploration and analysis on this theme.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This study aims to address the gap in the existing literature regarding the relationship between the educational aspirations of ethnic minority students in ethnic regions and social support. Specifically, the first objective of this study is to determine the relationship between the educational aspirations of ethnic minority students and social support. The second objective is to explore strategies to enhance the educational aspirations of ethnic minority students in ethnic regions. By achieving these two research objectives, this study aims to provide theoretical and practical support for understanding the factors influencing the formation of educational aspirations among ethnic minority students in ethnic regions and for enhancing their educational aspirations. This will contribute to informing and guiding the formulation and implementation of educational policies and practices.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research method, focusing on ethnic minority students in ethnic regions. Through the snowball sampling method, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 27 ethnic minority students to collect data. This study is conducted with the support of Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior. Participants exhibit different behaviors after receiving social support, which in turn influences their intention to pursue further education. The interview outline on social support in this study is adapted from Wang (2020) and consists of 13 questions, covering topics related to the current educational intentions of ethnic minority students, as well as various dimensions of social support including family, school, teachers, and societal policies. The collected interview data in this study were organized, coded, and analyzed. The interviewees, who are Chinese international students, are denoted as S, and their numbers range from S1 to S27. Meanwhile, this study takes ethnic minority students from a certain vocational college in Xinjiang in 2024 as research subjects, using a snowball sampling method. Different ethnic students will introduce their classmates or roommates from the same dormitory for online interviews. The study will compile and organize the interview information, categorize the results of the same questions, and identify the relationship between social support and the willingness to pursue further education.

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Finally, the interview results will be summarized and presented in tabular form. Based on this study, relevant

suggestions will be proposed to improve the willingness of ethnic minority students to pursue further education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study summarized the interview information and organized the participants' data, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Student Information

Number	Interviewee	Gender	Ethnicity	Intention to pursue further education
1	S1	Male	Uyghur	No
2	S2	Female	Uyghur	No
3	S3	Male	Kazakh	Yes
4	S4	Male	Uyghur	No
5	S5	Male	Kazakh	No
6	S6	Male	Kazakh	No
7	S7	Male	Kazakh	Yes
8	S8	Female	Tajik	Yes
9	S9	Female	Kazakh	No
10	S10	Female	Kazakh	No
11	S11	Male	Uyghur	No
12	S12	Female	Uyghur	No
13	S13	Male	Uyghur	No
14	S14	Male	Uyghur	Yes
15	S15	Male	Uyghur	Yes
16	S16	Male	Uyghur	No
17	S17	Female	Tajik	No
18	S18	Female	Tajik	No
19	S19	Female	Kazakh	Yes
20	S20	Male	Uyghur	No
21	S21	Male	Uyghur	No
22	S22	Male	Tajik	No
23	S23	Female	Uyghur	No
24	S24	Male	Uyghur	No
25	S25	Male	Uyghur	Yes
26	S26	Female	Kazakh	No
27	S27	Female	Kazakh	Yes

From the summary table of student information (Table 1), it can be seen that there were 27 interviewed students. Based on gender data, there were 11 females (40.7%) and 16 males (59.3%). Regarding the distribution of ethnicities, there were 14 Uyghur individuals (51.9%), 9 Kazakh individuals (33.3%), and 4 Tajik individuals (14.8%). This study primarily involved integrating and carefully reading all textual data to conduct preliminary organization and

analysis. The researcher mainly employed the method of open coding based on the interview outline by Wang (2020), reading through all textual data sentence by sentence, naming and labeling concepts according to the content of the sentences. Subsequently, through axial coding, similar labels were merged and categorized, followed by repeated comparisons to organize the main concepts (themes). Finally, in the stage of discovering correlations, this study sought

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relationships between categories, categorized and coded the data. questionnaire content and interviews, and anonymized the

Table 2. Interview Content

Interview Content		
Question	Ethnic minority students	Interview content
1.Do you think continuing your education is a very good choice for you personally?	S1	I think continuing my education is a good choice, but it's challenging for me.
	S2、 S3、 S5、 S6、 S7、 S8、 S9、 S11、 S13、S16、S17、S18、 S20、 S22、 S25、 S27	They believe continuing education is a good choice and want to try hard.
	S4、 S10、 S12、 S19、 S21	They believe it's more suitable to choose work after graduation.
	S26	I haven't made up my mind about this issue yet.
2.Do you believe that furthering your education can enhance your knowledge and professional skills?	S1-S27	They all believe that continuing education can enhance knowledge and professional skills.
3.Do you think continuing your education can help you obtain better job opportunities and higher salaries?	S4、 S10、 S12	Three students believe that furthering education may not lead to better job opportunities, while twenty-four students believe it can lead to higher income.
4.Are you eager to continue your education and further your studies?	S2、 S3、 S5、 S6、 S7、 S8、 S9、 S11、 S13、S16、S17、S18、 S20、 S22、 S25、 S27	They are eager to continue their education and further their studies.
	S1、 S4、 S10、 S12、 S19、 S21	They don't have the intention to continue their education for now.
	S26	I still need to consider this issue further.
5.Do your parents' opinions influence your willingness to continue your education?	S3、 S10、 S12、 S19	Four students believe they won't consider their parents' opinions regarding continuing education, while twenty-three students indicate they will seek their parents' opinions.
6.Does your parents' encouragement strengthen your determination to continue your education?	S1-S27	They all believe it's important to have their parents' support and encouragement for anything they do, including continuing education.
7.Will you decide whether to continue your education based on your family's financial situation?	S1-S27	They mention that financial support from their parents is necessary for tuition and living expenses, and they will consider their family's financial situation.

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8. Will you consider your parents' opinions when deciding whether to pursue further education?	S1, S4, S10, S12, S19, S21	They are clear that they will consider working first and not participate in further education exams.
9. Do teachers' opinions influence your willingness to continue your education?	S1-S27	They mention that teachers provide information about further education and they may feel inclined to apply, but they will consider objective factors such as their grades and family financial situation.
10. Do teachers' encouragement and assistance strengthen your determination to pursue further education?	S1-S27	They all agree that encouragement and assistance from teachers are important.
11. Will you consider teachers' advice when deciding whether to continue your education?	S1, S4, S10, S12, S19	Five students mention they won't follow teachers' advice.
12. Will national subsidy policies have a significant impact on your educational choices?	S2, S3, S5, S6, S7, S8, S9, S11, S13, S16, S17, S18, S20, S22, S25, S27	Most students believe that national subsidy policies for education can significantly help them and may influence their willingness to pursue further education.
13. Will factors such as the reputation of universities, majors, and faculty influence your educational choices?	S2, S5	They mention they don't mind the facilities of the school as long as they can continue their education.
	S9, S11, S13, S16, S17, S18, S20, S22, S25	They pay attention to factors such as the reputation of the school, the major, and the faculty, hoping to attend a better school for further study.

During the investigation process, this study utilized coding techniques to derive research results from Table 2. Specifically, the analysis was conducted from the following aspects.

1. The current status of ethnic minority students' intention to pursue further education

The research results from Table 2 indicate that among the 27 interviewed ethnic minority students, Student 26 mentioned, "I haven't thought about this question yet." Students 4, 10, 12, 19, and 21 expressed no intention to pursue further education at present. Twenty-one (78%) of the interviewed students affirmed their intention to pursue further education, stating that they would seize the opportunity if possible. During in-depth interviews on this issue, it was found that all students acknowledged that further education could enhance knowledge and professional skills. Students 4, 10, and 12 believed that pursuing further education might not necessarily lead to better job opportunities. In the interviews,

24 (89%) students believed that pursuing further education could lead to higher income. Overall, Students 1, 4, 10, 12, 19, and 21 stated that they currently have no intention to pursue further education, Student 26 expressed the need for further consideration, while the other 20 (74%) students expressed a willingness to continue their education.

2. The impact of social support on the intention to pursue further education

This study investigates the relationship between social support and the intention to pursue further education among ethnic minority students. From the summarized interview information presented in Table 2, it can be observed that the influencing factors of social support in this interview include parents, teachers, relevant policies, and schools. From the perspective of parental support, four students (S3, S10, S12, S19) believe that their decision to pursue further education does not depend on their parents' opinions, while

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23 students indicated that they would seek their parents' opinions. All 27 interviewed students consider parental support and encouragement important for any endeavor, including pursuing further education. They also acknowledge the financial support needed for tuition and living expenses and consider their family's economic situation.

In summary, in terms of whether to listen to their parents' opinions regarding further education, six students (S1, S4, S10, S12, S19, S21) stated that they would adhere to their own views and not heed their parents' advice. However, 21 (78%) students consider their parents' opinions important. Regarding teacher support, all interviewees indicated that teachers would influence their intention to pursue further education. They feel motivated to apply whenever encouraged by teachers but consider objective factors such as their academic performance and family's financial situation. However, five students (S1, S4, S10, S12, S19) stated that they would not follow their teachers' advice. From the perspective of support from relevant policies, most students believe that national subsidy policies can significantly assist their pursuit of further education and influence their intentions. Sixteen (59%) students consider national policies as a factor in their decision-making process. Lastly, concerning the choice of the school for further education, two students (S2, S5) prioritize successful admission over factors such as the quality of faculty, program, and reputation. Nine students focus on factors such as the school's reputation, program, and faculty, aiming to attend a prestigious institution. Sixteen students hold a neutral stance on the hardware and software conditions of the school.

3. Suggestions

This study examines the impact of social support on the intention to pursue further education among ethnic minority students using a case study of a modern industrial college in Xinjiang, China. The research results, derived from interview content, indicate that the majority of ethnic minority vocational students recognize the importance of continued education and express a desire to pursue further studies. In addition to concerns about their own career plans or academic performance, apprehensions about lacking the necessary conditions for further education, social support plays a significant role in shaping their intentions. Based on

the comprehensive findings, efforts from families, teachers, policies, and schools are recommended to provide more support and opportunities for ethnic minority vocational students, thereby fostering their willingness and enthusiasm to pursue further education.

3.1 Family Support

From the perspective of the family, parents not only provide economic support to students for further education but also offer emotional encouragement and assistance. The research results encourage parents to provide positive support and encouragement to their children, letting them know that their efforts are worthwhile. At the same time, the family environment should be conducive to learning and ambition, providing appropriate study spaces and resource support. Whether the family acknowledges the pursuit of further education or not will directly or indirectly manifest in daily communication with the students, influencing the intention of ethnic minority vocational students to pursue further education. This study suggests that parents should adopt a developmental perspective when considering their children's pursuit of further education, fostering a lifelong education mindset, and improving the effectiveness of family education methods to stimulate students' intention to pursue further education.

3.2 Teacher Support

As mentors both inside and outside the classroom, teachers play a crucial role in conveying information and influencing the intention of vocational students to pursue further education. The attitudes of teachers toward vocational students' further education significantly impact their intentions. Teachers should continually improve their own teaching qualifications, utilizing their own growth and development to positively guide and influence students' intentions to pursue further education. During teaching and student interaction, additional attention and support can be provided to ethnic minority students, offering personalized learning guidance and tutoring. Through regular individual meetings, teachers can understand students' learning situations and career plans, providing relevant advice and assistance.

3.3 Policy Support

In addition to existing national scholarships and financial aid programs, specialized incentives and support schemes for further education can be established. Local governments

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and schools should jointly address the issue of further education for ethnic minority students in ethnic regions by formulating and implementing inclusive policies. Specifically, collaboration with developed regions in China should be encouraged to establish joint training programs, promoting inter-regional cooperation. More opportunities should be provided for ethnic minority students to broaden their horizons, while respecting their lifestyles and cultures. Comprehensive measures should be taken to ensure their well-being and academic pursuits.

3.4 School Support

From the perspective of vocational colleges, schools can provide more career planning guidance and resources to help students understand different pathways and options for further education. Conducting promotional activities to showcase successful cases and role models can inspire students' ambition and confidence. The purpose of further education is to enhance professional skills through continued learning. Therefore, as educational institutions, schools need to create a diverse and inclusive campus environment where ethnic minority students feel welcomed and supported. Additionally, schools can attract high-quality teaching staff and design relevant courses based on the study duration for vocational students transitioning to undergraduate programs, thereby reflecting the characteristics and advantages of talent development programs.

SUMMARY OF RESULTS

The study concludes that the majority of ethnic minority vocational students in the ethnic regions have the intention to further their education, and this intention is influenced by social support. In other words, factors such as family, teachers, policies, and schools can influence the educational aspirations of ethnic minority vocational students. Combining the Theory of Planned Behavior, the study suggests that individuals are more likely to intend and eventually engage in a specific behavior when they have a positive attitude towards it, perceive strong subjective norms supporting the behavior, and believe they have control over it. The research concludes that the educational aspirations of ethnic minority students are influenced by social support.

Based on the analysis of the interview content, the study draws its conclusions. As shown in Table 1, the 27

interviewed ethnic minority students have a strong intention to further their education, with 78% of the students expressing such intention. The results of this study supported the studies by Gong et al. (2022) , He and Xiao (2024) in terms of the strong willingness of ethnic minority students to pursue further education. Regarding the relationship between social support and educational aspirations, the study's results are consistent with those of Tang (2023) , Kang and Gong (2024), indicating that educational aspirations are complex. Apart from internal factors such as academic performance and early employment in career planning processes, ethnic minority students' educational aspirations are influenced by various aspects of society.

Zhu and Wu (2021) and Wang and Chen (2023) have summarized the influence of family factors on educational aspirations, which is similar to the findings of this study. Through the organization of interview data, it was discovered that the majority of ethnic minority students consider their parents' opinions when contemplating further education, and they also take into account the family's financial situation. Another result obtained by this study is that the educational aspirations of ethnic minority students are influenced by teachers, national policies, and schools, all of which fall within the category of social support. These findings align with Kim and Jeon (2019) and McLeod et al. (2020), who suggest that social support can help ethnic minority students build self-esteem and confidence, better cope with stress and adversity. From the perspective of social support, the educational aspirations of ethnic minority students are influenced by encouragement and support from various sources, including family, teachers, policies, and schools. The results of this study are similar to those of Pu et al. (2024) and He (2024), suggesting that social support can predict individuals' perceptions and emphasizing the subjective perceptual abilities of individuals. The opinions of parents, family economic conditions, encouragement and assistance from teachers, relevant educational support policies, and various conditions of the schools they aspire to attend all play a role in influencing the educational aspirations of ethnic minority students. Handling these issues well can positively guide students to pursue further education, thereby improving the overall level of professional knowledge, promoting progress and

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development in ethnic minority areas.

CONCLUSION

This study focuses on the educational aspirations of ethnic minority vocational students in ethnic regions, supplementing the existing research on educational aspirations. It explores the relationship between social support and educational aspirations, drawing conclusions closely related to family, teachers, policies, and schools, prompting attention to various aspects of social support. It provides some assistance and reference for the continued education of ethnic minority vocational students. Increasing the willingness of ethnic minority vocational students to pursue further education can help more students enhance their educational levels, acquire specialized knowledge, and broaden their horizons, thus overall elevating the educational attainment of ethnic minority students. Simultaneously, fully implementing education policies aimed at regional economic development in China can promote the development of minority areas and their economies. The results of this study can be extrapolated to other schools in ethnic minority areas, and it is hoped that future scholars will broaden their research scope and geographical focus, providing valuable insights for enhancing the overall cultural and professional skills of ethnic minority students in these regions. Furthermore, this study also serves as a reference for researchers to expand their scope, increase sample sizes, and better assist ethnic minority students in continuing their education in the future.

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